

```

contract MoneySupplyTax is Coin {

    uint period = 365 days;
    uint taxrate = 1 - 1/period;
    mapping(address => uint) taxDeclared;

    function collectTax(uint undeclared) internal {
        balanceOf[address(this)] += totalSupply - totalSupply*undeclared;
    }
    function enforceTax(address _account) internal {
        undeclared = taxrate**(block.timestamp - taxDeclared[_account]);
        balanceOf[_account] *= undeclared;
        if(_account == address(this)) collectTax(undeclared);
        taxDeclared[_account] = block.timestamp;
    }
    function payment(address _to, uint _amount) public {
        enforceTax(msg.sender);
        enforceTax(_to);
        transfer(_to, _amount);
    }
    function taxFaucet() public {
        enforceTax(address(this));
    }
}

```